

Pancreatic Tumor Medical Image Segmentation using Cuckoo Search Optimization Algorithm

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Abstract

The process of improving an image's quality and attractiveness to provide a better transfer representation for various automated images in the future, like satellite and aerial photos, medical images, and images with weak contrast and noise, is known as image optimization. Numerous image optimization techniques, like Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Ant Bee Colony (ABC) optimization, and, more recently, the Cuckoo Optimization Algorithm (COA), draw inspiration from nature. An efficient technique for swarm intelligence optimization is the Cuckoo Search (CS) algorithm. When it comes to tackling optimization difficulties, the COA technique is incredibly effective. COA is distinct from the way of life and traits of the Cuckoo Sparrow society. In this article, Cuckoo algorithm is used for image segmentation to obtain an enhanced image of pancreatic tumor. The algorithm outperforms according to experimental results. The improved CT scans aid in the early detection and diagnosis of pancreatic cancer.

Keywords: Cuckoo search, Preprocessing, Pancreatic tumor, Region based Segmentation, Threshold

1.Introduction

Image segmentation is an important part of image processing that can be challenging to master. To break an image into meaningful chunks with similar qualities and properties, a technique known as "image segmentation" is used. The basic goal of segmentation is simplification, which entails presenting an image in a way that makes sense and is easy to analyze. The segmentation of an image is the first step in its analysis. Image segmentation divides an image into sections or segments that share similar qualities or properties. There are three approaches to image segmentation: the Region approach, the Edge approach, and the Data clustering technique. An image is separated into discrete pieces based on their degree of resemblance using a similarity detection-based approach. This strategy combines thresholding, region-growth, and splitting and merging techniques. All of these methods divide the image into portions with the same pixels. An image is segmented into sections based on where the lines begin and terminate using a method based on discontinuity detection. Edges caused by variations in intensity are discovered and matched to the edges of regions in edge-detection-based segmentation. The region approach is used to detect similarity, while edge detection and boundary detection are used to detect

discontinuity [1]. The various classification techniques are discussed in this section as displayed in Fig 5.1.

Fig 5.1. Classification of Image Segmentation Techniques

2.Related Work

E A Pambudi et al [2] to process, guarantee convergence, and strengthen the K-Means weak side, employ a grey wolf optimizer. The initialization cluster centre was found using the fitness value Sum Square Error (SSM). In order to lower the SSE of the population and searches, Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) was used in new position. Wentan Jiao et al [3] improved cuckoo search (ICS) multithreshold segmentation technique. The size factor is optimized to increase the possibility of finding the optimal solution, the number of possible solutions is increased using a chaotic population initialization, and the probability is employed to reduce the complexity of the algorithms. Wei Liu et al [4] in order to determine the optimal staggered edges for picture splitting, Renyi's entropy as the wellbeing work is calculated using a meta-heuristic approach. Six additional traditional and novel transformational calculations are compared with analyses of four concrete filtering techniques used to the small number of images. Yuan Xu et al [5] automatically dividing apart ultrasound pictures of the breasts. Quantitative metrics for evaluating segmentation outcomes, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1measure, all surpassed high expectations, demonstrating the method's ability to distinguish between functional tissues in breast ultrasound images.

3.Segmentation Techniques

3.1 Region Based Segmentation

This segmentation method groups pixels that belong to the same item together [6]. The edge flow is turned into a vector once the color and texture change has been determined. The edges

are calculated from this in order to progress [7]. The thresholding technique is crucial for regional segmentation. Segmentation should only be present in the area that is enclosed. Region-based segmentation is another name for similarity-based segmentation [8]. The boundaries for segmentation are predetermined. At each level, at least one pixel related to the area is taken into account [9]. Missing edge pixels will not result in a gap in this region-based segmentation [10].

3.2 Edge Based Segmentation

Edge detection methods can also be used to split items. The border of the segment is determined using this procedure. Edges are identified in order to identify image breaks. The edges of the area are established by calculating the value of each pixel and comparing it to the values of the pixels around it. Both the fixed and adaptive components of the Support Vector Machine (SVM) [11] are used for this categorization. Segmentation is a two-step process: first, the edge detector is used to gather edge information, and then the pixels are named. This technique also has the advantage of obtaining information from the porous border [12]. The discovered edges are not required to be closed in edge-based segmentation. To segment the image, various edge detectors are used. Edges are the gaps in intensity perception that reveal how an object is formed. When the intensities are known precisely, every object in the image can be tracked [15]. The image is fragmented according to how the edges flow. It denotes the direction in which the color and texture of a pixel change [13]. Edges can also be used to separate things. There will be a gap between the edges because it is not closed. Edge joining thus bridges the gap. Broken edges are stretched along the slope to provide a link for segmentation [14].

3.3 Feature Based Segmentation

Clustering is an alternate segmentation approach. After performing clustering, the image was converted into a histogram [16]. Fuzzy C is an unsupervised method for segmenting color pictures by pixel clustering. This is the format for standard images. Fragmentation occurs in an image that is noisy [17]. To divide textured images, the simple clustering algorithm K-means is implemented. It creates image portions by grouping pixels that are similar [18]. To partition items, feature clustering is used, and in this case, the colors of the parts are changed [19]. The look of the image is also fully liable for segmentation [20]. Several considerations are addressed while segmenting. For segmentation, the difference between intensity and color value is used [21]. They use the Fuzzy Clustering technique to segment a color image, which forms color clusters using the

fuzzy membership function in color space in connection to image space. The method works well for determining the color region [22]. Clustering is used to partition things in real time. A virtual attention zone is precisely captured for segmentation [23]. Multi-thresholding divides an image into many portions. Then, to fix the problem, Fuzzy C-Means Clustering is used. This benefit applies to all multispectral images [24]. K-Means Clustering is a way of partitioning regions for the goal of growth [25]. Color space decision factors in the shape of cylinders are used in the Clustering technique for image segmentation. Surfaces are determined using histograms, while clusters are identified using thresholding. Seeded Growing Region is used for segmentation (SRG). One challenge is that pixels must be sorted before they can be labeled. To circumvent this problem, SRG invented a technique called "oriented parallel pixel tagging."

3.4 Threshold Based Segmentation

The most basic approach of classification is to use thresholds. The threshold values are determined using the histogram of the original image's edges [28]. To calculate threshold values, an image with detected edges is used. Assuming the threshold and edge detections is correct. Thresholding is easier to implement than other methods since it requires less mathematics. [26] To split objects, the phrase "his ton" is used. A collection of pixels known as "his tons" may exist for a specific segment. The roughness of an image is measured first, followed by a thresholding procedure. To classify items, adaptive thresholding is utilized. The thresholding surface is then supplemented with the grey level points with the largest gradient. This image segmentation approach cannot be used on images that are too complicated.

3.5 Model Based Segmentation

Model-based segmentation is also known as Markov Random Field (MRF)-based segmentation. A region smoothness restriction is included in MRF, which is used for color segmentation. Color pixel tuples components are regarded as independent random variables for later processing. Edges can be found with increased precision when MRF is paired with edge detection [27]. MRF has a space smoothness limitation, and there are color component correlations. The parameter value of the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm is determined through unsupervised operation. A little fraction of the image is used in resolution-based segmentation. Segmentation can also be done with the Gaussian Markov Random Field (GMRF), which takes into account the interdependence of pixels in space. The Gaussian Markov Model

(GMM) is used for segmentation in region expansion. Within the GMM framework, an extension of the Gaussian Markov Model (GMM) identifies both region and edge cues. The feature space is also identified using this technique.

4 Pancreatic Tumor Detection Through Image Processing

The identification of important molecular linkages and genes that contribute to disease progression is currently a major concern. Considering pancreatic cancer, a novel technique is being developed to discover the critical molecular networks [28] and proteins in the progression of an infection with diverse stages of tumor tissue and monastic pancreatic tumors. The Filter approach is used during the normalization phase to choose the correct genetic component and delete duplicate genes. Following preprocessing, three distinct spectral clustering techniques are employed. Pancreatic adenocarcinoma is a prevalent form of pancreatic cancer. This is present in 90% of all human pancreatic tumors. It is said to be the worst disease, with only 3-5% of those who contract it surviving. In recent years, numerous cancer detection approaches based on deep learning have been created. On the basis of the spontaneous detection of pancreatic tumors, computed tomography (CT) is frequently utilized to diagnose and treat pancreatic cancer. The results of this study reveal that there are successful treatments for pancreatic cancer patients. This analysis could be extended based on the patient's state in order to acquire the most accurate results.

5. Image Segmentation in the Proposed Work

Segmentation is the process of separating the basic pieces of a digital image. The basic objective of segmentation is to develop and/or transform an image's representation into something that is more significant and easier to inspect. This is accomplished by segmenting the image into smaller, more manageable pieces. The proposed study incorporates a spatial region-based segmentation technique. This approach generates segments by dividing a picture into fragments containing similar characteristics. The primary objective of this method is to identify certain seed regions, which can be a small or large fraction of the input image. Then, particular ways to increase or reduce the number of pixels is implemented. Consequently, there are two straightforward operations that can be executed using this method. These are known as region growth, region split, and region merge, respectively. When constructing an area, the technique begins with a smaller set of pixels before combining or accumulating them depending on some resemblance criterion. This procedure is done until the desired size of the region is achieved. Consequently, this method

is known as bottom-up. The region growth approach is implemented by comparing the current pixel to its adjacent pixels. The technique begins by selecting a random seed pixel from the input image. If a similarity is found during this comparison, the pixel in question is linked to the seed pixel, and the targeted region expands significantly. Once the target number is reached, there will be no additional room for growth. The algorithm will now select a new seed pixel and restart the procedure. Edge detection is a time-consuming and labor-intensive process; however, for images with more outliers, region expanding techniques are preferable. Figure 5.2 shows region-based segmentation.

Fig 5.2. Region-based Segmentation

The splitting approach involves frequently dividing an image into a number of subsections with no shared characteristics. Merging is the technique of combining contiguous sections that are reasonably comparable to one another. In contrast to region growth, this method takes the complete image into account. This method resembles the divide and conquer tactic. At this point, just the splitting procedure has been completed. Merging is essential to achieve a comprehensive outcome. After the phase of splitting, a number of visually identical patches began to spread throughout the images. To finish the image, the merging technique is now applied. After each pause, the comparison process will begin, taking into account the proximity of nearby locations. If required, merge operations are done on the basis of identical characteristics. The main issue of the strategy is excessive segmentation. When the image contains a greater number of outliers or an intensity deviation, it is more difficult to detect the shielding of the genuine images; hence, the operation requires more time and energy. Figure 5.3 shows the region-based segmentation used to detect the tumor.

Fig 5.3. Detection of tumor using Region-based Segmentation

6. Cuckoo Search

Cuckoos are intriguing not just for their extraordinary vocalizations, but also for their aggressive breeding strategy. The CS algorithm, a population-based, heuristic evolutionary algorithm, was developed. On the other hand, host birds that come into direct touch with invasive species may reject to incubate eggs of other species. In this circumstance, they will either entirely demolish the nests and construct new ones elsewhere, or abandon the old nests and discard them. Some cuckoo species have evolved to the point where female parasitic cuckoos can mimic the hues and patterns of a particular group of host species' eggs. This allows these cuckoos to decrease the likelihood that their eggs will be rejected by their host species while simultaneously enhancing their reproductive success. Additionally, research has showed that a cuckoo chick can imitate the noises of host chicks to get access to additional feeding opportunities. This unique and peculiar pattern of breeding behavior is a metaphor for the cuckoo's meta-heuristics approach to tackling optimization problems.

6.1 Cuckoo Algorithm

We provide a strategy for edge-enhanced scaling that emphasizes a convolutional neural network and hybrid cuckoo search technique. It is anticipated that this would replace a time-consuming and labor-intensive machine learning technique for the image processing system, which requires extensive, sophisticated training on a vast scale. The Cuckoo Search (CS) process is utilized to enhance the image's input components. After that, the image quality will be enhanced to a higher grade. The CS approach was initially applied to the initial cuckoo population. These cuckoos intend to lay their eggs within the eggshells of the swarming birds.

Algorithm 1: Cuckoo Algorithm

Input: Quantity of populace p

Output: enhancement of input constraints

- 1 *Set an arbitrary populace of p host*
 - 2 *Random cuckoo generation i*
 - 3 *Estimate the corresponding Fitness, Fi*
 - 3 *Choose a nest among parbitrarily, j*
 - 4 *if (Fj <=Fi)*
 - 5 *set j as solution*
 - 6 *Execute - Frontward model ;Geometrical twist Operator; Operator corresponds to down sampling*
 - 7 *Improve the above factor for the chosen image*
 - 8 *Reset j by the updated value*
 - 9 *Unrestraint a fraction, Pa of inferior nests and construct the updates ones*
 - 10 *Retain the existing best*
 - 11 *If (highest iteration<=t)*
 - 12 *Discover the best result*
- Return:** *with enhancedfactor*

7. Evaluation Metrics

Accuracy

It is used to measure the correct predicted values from the total values evaluated by fraction in Equation 7.1

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN} \quad (7.1)$$

Precision

This method is used to measure the true prediction from the total of both true and false predicted values. It is calculated as in Equation 7.2

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (7.2)$$

Recall

This method is used to calculate the right proportion of the data in Equation 7.3

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TN + TP} \quad (7.3)$$

Similarity Index Measure

This method is used to represent the structural changes in the images in Equation 7.4

$$SSIM = \frac{(2\mu_f\mu_j + C_1) \cdot (2\sigma_{f,j} + C_2)}{(\mu_f^2 + \mu_j^2 + C_1) \cdot (\sigma_f^2 + \sigma_j^2 + C_2)} \quad (7.4)$$

8. Results And Discussion

Input images are segmented as shown in the Figure 5.5. The results of the proposed work will be discussed based on four parameters namely accuracy, precision, recall rate and time

duration. The proposed algorithm Cuckoo Algorithm is compared with other existing algorithms namely Traditional Cuckoo Search (TCS), Particle Swarm Optimization. The resulting data values are displayed in Table 5.2.

Fig 5.5. Segmented image of pancreatic tumor

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision rate	Recall Rate	Time Duration
TCS	89.47	7.09	6.41	0.412
PSO	91.44	7.89	7.59	0.353
CS	97.82	9.32	8.78	0.296

Table 5.2. Comparison on the parameters of the existing and proposed techniques

Fig 5.6. Accuracy of the proposed and existing algorithms

Pixel Accuracy (PA) is a statistic for semantic segmentation that reflects the number of correctly classified pixels in a picture. This metric measures how many of the image's pixels have been accurately labeled. This statistic computes the percentage of an image's total number of pixels that have been correctly categorized as a function of the image's total number of pixels. Fig. 5.6 demonstrates that the proposed method outperforms the existing ones in terms of accuracy.

Precision describes the accuracy of our positive detections relative to the truth. The precision of an algorithm is determined by how many of the predicted objects in a given image had a ground-truth annotation that matched the prediction. Recall accurately shows the extent to

which our optimistic forecasts match reality. The recall rate measures how many positive predictions we captured from all of the things highlighted in our ground truth. Precision (also known as positive predictive value) is the fraction of relevant instances among the recovered instances, whereas recall (also known as sensitivity) is the proportion of relevant instances retrieved. Relevance therefore dictates precision and recall.

Fig 5.7. Precision rate of the proposed and existing algorithms

Figure 5.7 displays a comparison of the proposed and existing approaches' precision levels. The proposed algorithm has a higher precision rate of 9.32, while the other existing works have lower precision rates. This demonstrates that the proposed methodology outperforms existing methods. Similarly, Fig 5.8 compares the recall rate of the proposed algorithms to that of the existing methods. According to the results, the suggested cuckoo algorithm has an effective recall rate of 8.78, which is greater than the other existing works, which demonstrate a decline in recall rate.

Fig 5.8. Recall rate of the proposed and existing algorithms

Fig 5.9. Time duration of the proposed and existing algorithms

The duration of time required to execute segmentation is provided. The default segmentation duration is 0.5 seconds. The suggested technique is faster than existing algorithms since it can finish its process in 0.296 seconds, whereas existing algorithms require longer time. The particulars are presented in Table 5.2 and Figure 5.9.

Taking into account the findings of all four parameters, we conclude that the newly proposed Cuckoo search optimization algorithm performs better than the existing algorithms. The results demonstrate that the suggested technique decreases computation time while generating more accurate and exact results.

8 Conclusion

Pancreatic cancer is a prominent cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide. Tumors of the pancreas that are malignant can drastically shorten the lives of those affected. Categorization of tumors is difficult without human assistance. In this article input images of pancreatic cancer are segmented using region-based segmentation (RBS) and Cuckoo Search Algorithm. Results are evaluated using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and Time. At present only limited datas are used for testing. In future more datas will be used and new optimization techniques are implemented to get better results.

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